

Navigating Challenges and strategies for data sharing and integration in the Data Space Era

A vision out from workshop held at Data Week 2025

July 2025

Introduction

The potential of data sharing, particularly through Data Spaces, offers significant opportunities for the innovation community to address societal and business challenges. However, numerous obstacles must be navigated to effectively unlock this potential.

In the last Data Week 2025 the projects under the HORIZON-CL4-2023-DATA-01-02 topic (CyclOps, DS2, CEDAR, NOUS and PLIADES) organized a workshop focused on identifying the critical challenges faced by industry and stakeholders in achieving seamless data sharing and leveraging Data Spaces across various sectors and domains; and explore innovative strategies to overcome these obstacles. The workshop aimed at putting together the insights obtained so far by the bird-of-a-feather projects and broadening its scope with the insights from the audience captured during the workshop to allow a more holistic discussion and scene around the topic.

The discussion was organized in three main blocks, starting with a first block focused on getting a better understanding of who is the user of the different solutions that are being created to allow for data sharing, integration and leverage Data Spaces, and what is their expected added value sought. Once the users were identified, the discussion moved to the barriers to delivering value and the main pain points these users find. The third block allowed to share innovative approaches the projects are developing to overcome selected obstacles, and how these solutions contribute to Data Spaces and align with the DSSC blueprint and its building blocks.

This paper collects the main insights shared and discussed during the workshop from both the projects and the audience, constituting a rich compendium of diverse perspectives and approaches that help illuminate the current landscape and offer perspectives for future work on the area.

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27 May / 14:00–15:30 EEST / Room 1

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Navigating the Data Seas

27 – 28 May / Athens

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The user profile and their expected added-value

There are a plethora of use cases and plenty of users and stakeholders that can benefit from data sharing, integration and Data Spaces. In the workshop, the first objective was to identify the primary users of the tools—those for whom the solutions should be designed and those who will directly interact with Data Spaces; and the value they expect to gain from data sharing, integration and Data Spaces. This exercise also helps distinguish these users from other roles and organizational profiles within the data ecosystem that may benefit indirectly.

Each project has identified its key user profiles, which—together with the user perspectives represented by the audience—allow us to draw broader conclusions about the overall user landscape.

Projects background and targeted end-users

CyclOps aims to accelerate the adoption and production of data, models, and services within and for data spaces. The project's core objective is to enable secure and efficient data sharing and exchange by delivering interoperable and trustworthy automation for the management, governance, and maintenance of the entire data life cycle, especially for large-scale, heterogeneous, and distributed data sources. The CyclOps platform automates the creation of data processing pipelines—from ingesting data from multiple sources to delivering ready-to-use data, models, and services tailored for data spaces. At the heart of this approach lies the use of knowledge graphs, a robust semantic formalism.

Moreover, CyclOps integrates a comprehensive suite of tools for automated data management, distributed processing, AI model deployment, data space interoperability, and a human-centric interface to ensure usability and accessibility. The platform's capabilities will be validated through four real-world use cases aligned with key EU Data Spaces: Tourism and Mobility, Green Deal, Public Procurement, and Manufacturing.

CyclOps set of tools is targeted to any organization that want to leverage, cross and merge their data with data from relevant dataspace to (i) extract insights (research-oriented purpose) and (ii) create value-added services for their clients (business-alike purpose). The CyclOps framework is mainly addressed to data scientists: users that are responsible for implementing and managing the data pipelines that take data from diverse sources and process it to generate specialized AI models or other insights. These users traditionally deal with the technical aspects of pipeline orchestration and data integration. They can use the framework to define pipelines, and execute the models, ultimately delivering actionable insights with less manual effort. Another important user group includes knowledge scientists and domain experts, who typically manage the creation and handling of semantic assets, crucial for data integration and interoperability. CyclOps minimizes the need for their manual input to handle complex integration processes by automating much of the metadata generation, data connection and governance-related processes. CyclOps also offers functionalities to business users, that will be able to make high-level queries over the data once the platform is set-up and configured.

DS2 develops a modular infrastructure to cater for the diversity of data spaces, enabling seamless cross-sector data sharing while ensuring data sovereignty and compliance with European regulations. The Intersector DataSpace Toolkit (IDT), a decentralized architecture comprises of Broker to manage fail-safe Data Space operations and Modules which facilitate data lifecycles, incl. filtering, labeling, and human-in-the-loop processes. The project also develops Data Space Business Models with focus on earning logic and Data and Information assets Productization. The DS2's framework is validated through three intersectoral pilots: (i) City Scape: Focuses on modeling greenhouse gas emissions in urban environments, demonstrated in Cluj Napoca, Romania; (ii) Green Deal: Analyzes

the impact of agriculture, traffic, industry, and households on air pollutants, with a pilot in Murska Sobota, Slovenia; (iii) Precision Agriculture: Enhances agricultural data sharing and analysis, piloted in Greece; and (iv) Intersector: A dynamic use case combining elements from the above pilots to demonstrate cross-sector interoperability.

The DS2 has 6 Data spaces in 3 domains, hence instead of ideal user profile the focus is on serving all user types i.e. the “universal user”. In many cases the data providers and consumers are the same, they are called prosumers. We’ve discovered this type of user profiles in universities, in agri-food industry and among the public services providers in cities. Another major role in any data space is the Facilitator, or Operator who takes care of the overall secure and compliant operations of the environment. Other identified user profiles are traffic and mobility solution providers, households, energy and environmental footprint stakeholders and 3rd sector organisations. To enlarge and extend the user groups and segments it’s important to focus on user experience, landing pages and high quality of GUI’s. Second observation and discussion point also at the workshop was the user and usage safety and the focus on onboarding, solid governance and contracts.

CEDAR develops solutions that build and exploit Common European Data Spaces and Robust AI to enable transparent public governance. The world is currently confronting unprecedented challenges, encompassing global pandemics, ongoing conflicts, and environmental and energy crises. In response to these crises, there has been a significant surge in emergency public spending, accompanied by a relaxation of due diligence checks and oversight. Consequently, this has given rise to patterns of corruption and fraudulent activities, exerting profound and detrimental impacts on the European economy, society, environment, and politics. CEDAR sees these challenges as catalysts for research, innovation, and collaboration. Towards this goal, CEDAR aims to: (i) Identify, collect, generate, harmonize, synchronize, protect and share large-scale, high-quality and value datasets that will support the goals of transparent public governance; (ii) Improve methods and tools for effective data management and ML Operations; (iii) Develop new AI and ML data analytics methods for robust, data-efficient, human-centric and fact-based decision making; (iv) Validate the results with relevant public and private stakeholders in 3 different pilot situations - Monitoring of National Recovery and Resilience Plan Funds in Italy, Monitor Slovenia’s Public Healthcare funds, Monitor the transparent management of foreign aid for rebuilding Ukraine.

CEDAR examines solutions for a set of actors that have different levels of access on procurement procedures and access rights on external data sources. In the case of Italy, these are regional government directors or regional department employees that need to have access to data and analysis results for specific subsets of the procurement procedures, as well as public buyers profiles such as the Procurement Manager of a Municipality. In the case of Slovenia, employees with similar access rights are the procurement officers of the hospitals and healthcare providers. However, in this pilot we also examine user actors with a wider view of the data and more advanced rights in accessing data and analysis results, such as the ministry of health auditors, or the ministry of interior and the police forces. Suppliers and bidders i.e. private companies may also need partial access to CEDAR data space platform and AI components to be aware of the competition and to have a transparent understanding of the active or closed tenders. The IT dept. of the ministry of digital transformation has a totally different need since the IT admin users need to monitor the data sharing from different public data sources. Finally, in the case of Ukraine, the Anti-corruption and Law-Enforcement officers need to be able to analyse and identify corruption links among the stakeholders and automate fraud detection and procurement monitoring to safeguard reconstruction funds and support anti-corruption efforts. As such the 3 main user actors of CEDAR are: public officers in different access tier, individuals and private companies that monitor the transparency of tender procedures, IT admins and developers that need to monitor the data sharing of public data sources.

NOUS is developing the architecture of a European Cloud Service that allows computational and data storage resources to be used from edge devices as well as supercomputers, through the HPC network, and Quantum Computers.

NOUS is an Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS)/Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS) cloud provider, harnessing edge computing and decentralisation paradigms to incorporate a wide array of devices and machines in its computational flow to provide leaps in Europe's capability to process vast amounts of data. The pipeline of the NOUS in the project includes three types of components: i) computational components that are responsible for executing computations; ii) edge components that are responsible for communicating with edge devices (such as IoT sensors/ actuators/ devices); and iii) data storage components that are responsible for data storage and storage management.

In the NOUS ecosystem, a diverse set of actors collaborate to enable a powerful, distributed cloud computing environment. Each actor plays a distinct but interconnected role, contributing to a dynamic and resource-rich infrastructure. Data providers form the foundation by sharing valuable datasets—ranging from sensor data to research archives—that fuel applications and services within NOUS. These datasets become accessible assets within the ecosystem, enabling innovation and analytics at scale. Infrastructure providers contribute computational power by offering access to their resources, which can include edge devices, high-performance computing (HPC) systems, and quantum computers. They enable the execution of complex workloads and support the scalability of applications across heterogeneous environments. Application providers, on the other hand, offer ready-to-use software tools, algorithms, and services that operate within the NOUS platform. These applications are made available to end users, who are the final consumers of the ecosystem's offerings. End users leverage the shared data, run applications, and utilize computing resources to solve problems, generate insights, and drive digital transformation across sectors. Together, this network of actors forms a collaborative ecosystem that enhances Europe's digital and data-processing capabilities.

PLIADES is focused on optimizing AI-enabled data lifecycles optimization & integrating data spaces to enhance efficiency and interoperability. The project aims to develop and deploy AI-driven technologies across a wide range of data used in both single-domain and cross-domain applications, spanning sectors including Mobility, Energy, Industry, Healthcare and Green Deal.

PLIADES addresses the entire data lifecycle – from creation to exchange –, by introducing novel methods, models and abstractions for environmentally sustainable and context-aware data assets. It establishes a secure and seamless ecosystem for data sharing across diverse data spaces and leverages AI to automate privacy enforcement, usage policies and monitoring mechanisms, ensuring data sovereignty and trust throughout the entire lifecycle. Core component of PLIADES is the enhanced discoverability of data, through the incorporation of AI-driven ranking, querying and brokering schemes, that will operate in cross-domain scenarios and will enhance the overall data availability.

The primary users of the PLIADES framework are technically proficient professionals, who are already familiar with the concept of data spaces, but require advanced tools and infrastructure to enable secure, seamless and explainable data management across large-scale and complex environments. These users include data engineers, data scientists and AI developers – experts who understand the limitations of existing operational frameworks and are capable to incorporate emerging technologies into their workflows. IT departments and system integrators, along with R&D leads, researchers, engineers and technical managers are also key user groups, as they possess a comprehensive understanding of the data lifecycle – from data collection via IoT sensors, machines, or other sources, up to the generation of actionable analytics and insights that support organizational decision-making. Through the PLIADES framework, these users will be able to seamlessly access and utilize data from multiple domains, uncovering valuable cross-domain insights. AI-driven discovery and recommendation engines will help evaluate the relevance and suitability of available datasets, significantly reducing the time spent on manual search and selection, while also ensuring full data sovereignty and compliance with regulations, such as GDPR. PLIADES will empower users with high-quality tools that will allow them to enhance the quality and efficiency of their services, across diverse applications, including CCAM, HRI scenarios and clinical models analysis.

The profile of users in the audience and their insights

Workshop participants were asked to identify their role, whether as a data solution provider, data owner/source, or end-user of data-driven applications, and their profile as either technical (e.g., data Scientist, engineer, developer, architect) or business (e.g. Consultant, Product Manager, Innovation lead, etc.). The audience was composed primarily of Data Solution Providers, who made up the majority with 21 participants, including 13 with a technical profile and 8 with a business profile. Additionally, 7 representatives from Data Owners (mainly with business-oriented backgrounds) were present, alongside 8 end-users of data-based applications, also predominantly from a business profile (7 out of 8). The group was further complemented by the participation of one representative from BDVA, contributing a broader ecosystem perspective.

When asked about their expected added value, data solution providers and end-users of data-based applications share a common goal of unlocking the value of data, but their expectations differ in focus. Solution providers emphasise the need for high-quality, interoperable (FAIR) data, streamlined onboarding, trusted data-sharing environments (e.g., Data Spaces), and integrated infrastructures to enable AI, digital twins, and innovation across industries. Their priority lies in building the technical and organisational foundations that make data usable at scale. In contrast, end-users of data-based applications focus on the tangible outcomes of these efforts, seeking actionable data, faster access to reliable information, more accurate and robust AI tools, and better services that support clearer decision-making. While providers aim to create the conditions for innovation, users expect efficient, practical solutions that deliver immediate value in their workflows and business needs.

Discussion

Overall, the user landscape derived from the participant projects and the audience shows a diversity of profiles, spanning technical experts, institutional actors, business professionals, and community stakeholders, each with distinct roles and expectations in the data-sharing ecosystem. Among them, technical experts (e.g. data scientists, data engineers, AI developers) stand out as the main targeted users (relevant for CycLOps, PLIADES and NOUS). These users mainly seek operational efficiency (automation, reduce the manual effort) and scalability.

Other main group of users identified are business and public sector professionals (CEDAR and DS2 introduce broader user categories, including public officers, facilitators, and hybrid prosumers), whose expectations include to analyse and extract strategic insights from data, support decision-making and create new types of services. Across all these profiles, the expected value of data integration and sharing tools lies in enhanced data accessibility, improved interoperability, improved decision-making, and the ability to generate actionable knowledge across domains.

Challenges and barriers to obtain the expected added-value

Once the user profiles were discussed, the workshop moved on to discuss the main challenges and barriers faced by these users, starting from the insights from the participant projects in different domains. Each project shared the main points identified organized into five distinct areas covering the full data and AI lifecycle, going from and to Data Spaces and other data sources: Discovery & Ingestion, Data Integration, Data Processing, Data Usage / AI and Data Sharing. After that, the discussion was enlarged with the audience inputs.

Project's insights

All five projects reported challenges across the data value chain. Most of the issues were concentrated in the areas of Data Sharing, Data Discovery & Ingestion, and Data Usage / AI, though relevant obstacles were also identified in the areas of Data Integration and Data Processing. Besides, the lack of high-skilled profiles in all the required fields was also identified as a common challenge across all areas.

Data Sharing

Trust and Governance barriers

Challenges around trust in data sharing and the need for robust governance frameworks were widely highlighted. DS2 pointed to the importance of contracts, policies and agreements, CEDAR and PLIADES emphasized the lack of trust in publishing data and sharing across organisations and concerns regarding the compliance with increasingly complex data regulations (e.g., GDPR, MDR). NOUS also added challenges related to identity verification, trust establishment and governance compliance for joining Data Spaces, which can be time-consuming and resource-intensive for users.

Technical barriers to data Preparation and Publication

Both CycLOps and DS2 stressed the difficulties in preparing data, models, and services for publication in Data Spaces, and the work required on data productization so data owners can understand and control their data and information as value-driven assets. NOUS highlighted the need for specialized skills to handle data space connectors, which diverge from traditional IT practices. Communication and interoperability between different data spaces (DS-to-DS interaction) remains also technically challenging, limiting smooth data exchange and collaboration.

Limited Data Sharing Culture

DS2 identified a lack of culture and clear mandates for data sharing among data owners, which acted as a barrier at this stage.

Data Integration

Data Heterogeneity and Fragmentation

The integration of non-unified data, i.e., diverse data types and formats, including unstructured and semi-structured data, was a major obstacle identified by all projects (CyclOps, DS2, CEDAR, NOUS and PLIADES). CEDAR also commented the lack of homogenized data models, whereas PLIADES emphasized the absence of automated tools to harmonize datasets across stakeholders.

Lack of Standardized Procedures and Architectures

CEDAR also pointed out the absence of consolidated integration procedures and standardised architectural blocks that all cases can follow.

Discovery & Ingestion

Difficulties Finding Relevant Data and Data Space readiness

Both CEDAR and PLIADES reported difficulties to seamlessly connect different domains and enable effective discovery of data across cross-domain data spaces. NOUS and CEDAR also agree on challenges related to the scarcity of mature and operational data spaces, adding CEDAR the different digitisation maturity levels of public data sources, all in all, that limit discovery opportunities.

Metadata Quality, Vocabulary Standardization and context

DS2 highlighted as a persistent challenge the poor quality and accuracy of metadata and the lack of common vocabularies and data formats. Similarly, PLIADES noted that data shared within a single data space often lacks proper contextual information, such as semantic labels or domain-specific knowledge, reducing its usability and value.

Data Usage / AI

Data Quality and selection

On the one hand, both CEDAR and PLIADES reported that data quality is not always guaranteed, and the lack of standardized, high-quality, and well-described data assets might lead to uncertainty in data reliability and usability. On the other hand, CyclOps highlighted current challenges on selecting relevant datasets for specific purposes.

Regulatory and ethical concerns

DS2 highlighted the importance of addressing AI ethics and bias comprehensively and having well-defined contracts and policies. CEDAR notes the lack of a clear or easy roadmap for aligning AI components with the EU AI Act.

Technical Complexity in Advanced AI

Different complexities were also identified: NOUS identified challenges in implementing complex AI methods such as federated learning due to technical and organizational difficulties. CyclOps pointed to challenges in identifying relevant datasets and selecting appropriate AI algorithms and models for specific purposes. CEDAR stressed the lack of common methods for evaluating AI component performance across use cases.

Data Processing

Scalability and Efficiency

CyclOps noted the challenge of efficiently processing large volumes of data.

Limited Validation of Tools

CEDAR mentioned the existence of many tools, but they lack sufficient testing and validation for specific purposes, causing uncertainty in adoption.

Extended pain points identified by the audience

The discussion actively involved the audience, that was asked what the areas with more challenges were and to share specific pain points for them. Based on the received input, the most critical processes (in order of aggregated importance) were: Data Sharing (most frequently ranked among the top two positions), aligned with persistent challenges around trust, access, governance, and legal frameworks; Data Integration (frequently ranked first or second), showing the relevance of interoperability and difficulties merging disparate data sources into usable formats; Data Processing and Discovery & Ingestion; and, lastly, Data Usage / AI applications, indicating that the bottlenecks are found earlier in the pipeline (sharing, integration, processing) are blocking the progress toward advanced usage and AI. No significant differences were found among the perceptions from different groups of stakeholders.

Challenges shared by users were lack of standard tools and governance, limited data sharing and trust, regulatory and quality concerns, inadequate upskilling, and difficulties in accessing, preparing, and integrating high-quality, interoperable data for innovation and AI.

Discussion

The most challenging parts of the data lifecycle, according to the projects and workshop attendees, were Data integration and Data sharing. In particular, in Data Integration, data heterogeneity was identified as a significant bottleneck, and all projects reported challenges in the area. In the Data Sharing area, concerns regarding compliance and trust kept coming up during the session. Both projects and workshop participants highlighted challenges on preserving data privacy, compliance with current legal and evolving regulations and creating secure environments that encourage organizations to share their data keeping its control.

Clear priorities for future work are indicated by the consistent identification of governance issues and data heterogeneity across all projects.

The other areas, whereas not so popular, still included relevant issues like inadequate metadata, AI complexities or efficiency in processing, indicating other areas for improvement.

Strategic Opportunities Identified

During the workshop, the projects showcased how they are tackling their key challenges by presenting the specific solutions they are developing to address them. Each project highlighted its current approach to overcome the technical, operational, or governance-related barriers initially identified. For the sake of brevity, these solutions are not detailed in this paper, which instead focuses on the key discussion outcomes.

The exchange of strategies, together with the insights found during the workshop, both concerning end-user expectations and barriers, offer a valuable foundation for the projects and beyond to better align the solution development with the end-user and stakeholder needs, ensuring both relevance and long-term impact.

To shape the development of solutions, the projects can:

- Use the insights about trust and quality to embed governance mechanisms that address compliance, transparency, and accountability from the start, reducing user friction and build trust.
- Provide tools that can handle with harmonizing diverse data formats and structures through shared data models, semantic vocabularies, and automated integration tools, and ensure compatibility with multiple data space standards; as well connectors to enable seamless cross-domain data exchange.
- Leverage on the latest development of AI based tools and solutions. A synergetic and co-innovative approach to harnessing AI could help, not only to overcome current barriers but also set a precedent for future EU projects and clusters aiming to build interoperable, trustworthy, and user-centric data ecosystems.

For end-user and stakeholder engagement and sustainability, the session findings suggest:

- Tailor engagement strategies to different end-user profiles, recognising that data solution providers and end-users, as well as technical and business users require different forms of value and support.
- Include contextual help, tutorials, and best practices within the tools to support users with varying technical backgrounds, facilitating upskilling and adaptation.
- Demonstrate early value through pilot use cases, reflecting specific outcomes matching user expectations, helping build trust and drive broader adoption.
- Incorporate tools that bridge the gap between infrastructure and usability and clear interfaces for AI-ready data consumption.

Conclusion

The workshop brought together five projects and a wide range of stakeholders to explore the complexities of data sharing and integration and leveraging Data Spaces across various sectors and domains. The session examined user profiles and needs, key challenges, and project-driven solutions. The diversity of the projects enabled a rich and comprehensive discussion, further enhanced by the high level of participation of the audience through interactive surveys offering valuable insights.

The workshop revealed that there is a broad spectrum of users and stakeholders in the data ecosystem, with a major focus on technical experts. Despite their profile, users shared common priorities: accessing high-quality, interoperable data; enabling AI-driven innovation; and exploring new data-based business models.

The discussion also allowed to discover shared barriers for all users across projects and the audience, such as the complexities in data interoperability and the need for trust and legal clarity in data sharing.

Overall, the workshop provided valuable insights into the varying priorities across user groups, revealing both technical and business-driven expectations and actual concerns. These reflections not only support the projects in shaping practical, stakeholder-informed solutions but also reinforce the importance of cross-project collaboration and contribute to ongoing discussions within the BDVA ecosystem on advancing towards a more interoperable and trustworthy data ecosystem and how to build a trusted, federated data economy in Europe.

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Funded by
the European Union

These projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement numbers: DS2 101135967, CEDAR 101135577, CyclOps101135513, NOUS 101135927, PLIADES 101135988.